

GL MICAVE

D7.4 Report on the contribution to standardization

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Table of contents

Executive summary	4
List of tables.....	4
List of abbreviations.....	4
1. STRATEGY	5
1.1 General	5
1.2 Survey on Standardisation	6
1.3 Which committees have to be contacted?.....	7
1.4 What actions could be done?	8
1.4.1 Implication in technical committees	8
1.4.2 Informing technical committees	8
1.5 Planning of the actions to be carried out	8
2.CONCLUSIONS	9
3. REFERENCES	9

Executive summary

The standardisation activities of Task 7.4 are foreseen to be a facilitator of the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the GLOMICAVE platform, as well as a tool to improve the development and the exploitation strategy of the project. For this purpose, once studied in D7.3 the existing standards and technical committees related to GLOMICAVE, this deliverable D7.4 summarizes the actions carried out in the last six months (M7-M12).

NOTE This deliverable will be updated on the months M30 and M42.

List of tables

Table 1 –Main technical committees identified in D.7.3.	5
Table 2 –Proposed technical committees for dissemination activities.	6
Table 3 –Secretaries of the committees to contact.	7
Table 4 –Schedule and strategy for the development of the reviews of deliverable D7.4.	8

List of abbreviations

<i>AI</i>	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
<i>CEN</i>	<i>European Committee for Standardization</i>
<i>CENENLEC(CLC)</i>	<i>European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field</i>
<i>CLC</i>	<i>CENELEC</i>
<i>EN</i>	<i>European Standard</i>
<i>IEC</i>	<i>International Electrotechnical Commission</i>
<i>ISO</i>	<i>International Organization for Standardization; International Standard</i>
<i>SC</i>	<i>Subcommittee</i>
<i>TC</i>	<i>Technical Committee</i>
<i>TS</i>	<i>Technical Specification</i>
<i>UNE</i>	<i>Spanish Association for Standardization</i>

1. STRATEGY

1.1 General

Standardisation system is a huge combination of technical committees, standards, and procedures covering almost all possible aspects of the daily life.

To understand it and to make it something manageable for GLOMICAVE consortium, they were identified in deliverable D7.3 (about the standardisation landscape) those technical committees and standards that are related to GLOMICAVE project in some way.

Its conclusions were that there is a large number of mainly International technical committees, as well as of standards and project standards related to GLOMICAVE project that may be useful for its development and also for its future dissemination.

Despite there are not a specific standardization technical committee which activity impacts directly in the GLOMICAVE project, specific tasks to be addressed in the project are related with standardization works.

Depending on the assessment by GLOMICAVE partners of the impact of the identified standardization committees on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees and for the development of Deliverable D7.3 (Report on the contribution to standardization), several actions can be performed, for example:

- the follow up of the standardization activity through updates reported by UNE;
- the follow up through the joining of one or more GLOMICAVE representatives to the identified standardization committees. Standardization is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in a CEN/CENELEC/ISO/IEC technical committee through its National Mirror Committee and its National Standardization Body;
- the dissemination of the GLOMICAVE project progress by delivering reports to the relevant TCs Secretaries or by attending relevant technical committees' meetings.

With respect the dissemination activities, the most relevant committees are summarized in the following table:

Table 1 –Main technical committees identified in D.7.3.

Subject	Technical committee
Biogas	- ISO/TC 255 Biogas
Information technology	- ISO/IEC JTC1 Information technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC23 Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/ SC25 Interconnection of information technology equipment ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia, and hypermedia information ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC38 Cloud computing and distributed platforms ○ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence
Environmental management	- ISO/TC 207 Environmental management
Food products	- ISO/TC 34 Food products
Sludge recovery, recycling treatment and disposal	- ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal

1.2 Survey on Standardisation

To better understand GLOMICAVE's needs with respect to standardization, the following questions were asked to the partners, obtaining the results indicated after each one of them.

Participants: ADN, AkiNaO, AAU, ALLICE, ASEAVA, ASINCAR, EURECAT, FZJ, INRAE, KUL, NEC, TREE, SERIDA, UMINHO

1. Which technical bodies from the list above should we inform about the GLOMICAVE project?

The responses received to this question show that of all the committees that had been identified in deliverable D.7.3, only the following should be informed about the GLOMICAVE project:

Table 2 – Proposed technical committees for dissemination activities.

Subject	Technical committee
Biogas	- ISO/TC 255 Biogas
Information technology	- ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence
Environmental management	- ISO/TC 207 Environmental management
Food products	- ISO/TC 34 Food products
Sludge recovery, recycling treatment and disposal	- ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment, and disposal

2. Is your GLOMICAVE task affected by any European legislation (directives, regulations...)?

There is no specific European legislation or regulation that affects the tasks of GLOMICAVE. In France, as our partner AkiNaO tells us, sharka disease is regulated by the DRAAF (Direction Régionale de l'Alimentation, de l'Agriculture et de la forêt). To work with potentially infected plant material (_Prunus_) an authorization is required. (EU) 2019/829 and (EU) 2016/2031.

3. Does your organization participate in any technical committee for standardization from the previous list?

Only ASINCAR is working in the ISO/TC 34 Food products.

4. Based on your previous answer, please specify the technical body in which your organization is participating or would be interested in participating.

AkiNaO would be interested in participating on ISO / TC 207 Environmental management and UMINHO in ISO/TC 255 Biogas and ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment, and disposal.

5. Please chose, from the following answers, the reasons why you are participating or want to participate in the technical bodies:

- To influence in the content of standards according to my products / services
- To anticipate requirements affecting the products / services of my company
- To establish better levels of quality, performance, interoperability, etc.
- To make contacts with professionals from companies related to mine
- To make contacts with other stakeholders

Replies were the following:

- x1
- x1
- x2
- x2
- x2

6. Do you think that any aspect of your work on GLOMICAVE or the platform should be standardised?

Aspects that the partners think that should be standardized are data models and semantic interoperability for health and genomic domains.

7. Do you think that any of the GLOMICAVE deliverables developed (or future) could be interesting to be applied in the future by the animal, vegetal or environment industry?

These questions were asked thinking in the present and in the future, as some of these deliverables could be the draft for a future standardization. For the moment and taking into account the early stage of the project, this is not considered. It is important that the partners consider that some of the products or deliverables may be object to future standardisation.

8. An increasing number of standards based on patented technology are being successfully and widely developed. Nevertheless, to avoid patent rights problems that may arise when developing standards, CEN-CENELEC has developing a document to provide practical guidance on this subject. Do you know the Intellectual Property and Patents policies applied by CEN and ISO? ([CEN CENELEC IPR website](#) and [ISO IPR websites](#))

None of the partners knew the Intellectual Property and Patents policies applied by CEN and ISO.

9. Please, add any other information regarding your task/deliverables and standardisation that you may deem relevant.

There is no other information on tasks/deliverables and standardisation that GLOMICAVE partners consider relevant.

1.3 Which committees have to be contacted?

In deliverable D.7.3, a series of technical committees related to Biogas, Algorithm, API (Application Programming Interface), Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, were identified for a first approximation. Information Systems, Data Governance, Cloud, Cybersecurity, Genomics, Environment, Biomarkers, Food Products and Sludge that after reviewing the responses to the survey carried out among the partners it was seen that the committees that should be contacted are those that appear in Table 2 of this deliverable and whose secretariats are identified below.

Table 3 – Secretaries of the committees to contact.

Technical committee	Secretaries
- ISO/TC 255 Biogas	(China) Mr Baocheng Dong
- ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange	(USA) Mr Bill Ash
- ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence	(USA) Ms Heather Benko
- ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	(Canada) Mrs Christine Geraghty
- ISO/TC 34 Food products	(France) Mme Sandrine Espeillac
- ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment, and disposal	(France) Mr Arnaud Gaudrier

1.4 What actions could be done?

1.4.1 Implication in technical committees

With respect the specific actions to be carried out for the subsequent development of deliverables of month 30 and month 42, it is defining the different ways for participating in a technical committee that could be interesting for GLOMICAVE project and partners, and the grade of implication:

- a) the follow up of the standardisation activity through updates reported by UNE. This could be the case of the committees identified in the deliverable D.7.3.
- b) the follow up through the joining and participation of one or more GLOMICAVE representatives to a standardisation committee. Standardization is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in a CEN/CENELEC/ISO/IEC technical committee through its National Mirror Committee and National Standardization Body. This could be the case of ISO/TC 215/SC1 *Genomics informatics* and the participation of EURECAT, UMINHO or Allice. This technical body has approved the development of the technical specification ISO/PWI TS 8392 "Genomics Informatics. Description Rules for Genomic Data for Genetic Detection Products and services"

This proposal is based on the actual situation of industry data production, combined with the needs of upstream and downstream industry users. Solving the problem of data scope and semantic unification can enhance the data association ability, ensure information exchange, data flow, improve the data quality from the aspects of data integrity, validity and so on, and lay a good foundation for subsequent data storage, data application and data sharing. For this reason, this document will specify the requirements on the category definition and quality assessment of genomic data, including the content structure, attribute and description rules of data format, and the compilation rules of data format.

This document will be applied to genomic data processing and analysis and to the quality evaluation/assessment for genomic data. It is important for GLOMICAVE project that one or more partners work in the development of this Technical Specification (TS).

- c) The establishment of a Project Liaison with a Technical Committee. Under this figure, the consortium could participate as an entity in the TC works, without voting rights. Also, this implies an economic cost.

1.4.2 Informing technical committees

The specific actions identified at the beginning of the activities of this report were those related to the information to the relevant technical committees about the project.

The objective is to familiarize the technical committees with the GLOMICAVE project, trying to involve them and taking possible opinions into account. For this purpose, already available public material will be used.

For these purposes, UNE will contact the secretariats identified in Table 3 of this report to disseminate the progress of the GLOMICAVE project, delivering general reports to the Secretariats of the relevant TCs and, if possible, add specific promotional material for each TC identified.

1.5 Planning of the actions to be carried out

With all the previously presented information, a planning for implementation of the strategy contained in this document was performed, to develop the reviews of deliverable D7.4.

Table 4 – Schedule and strategy for the development of the reviews of deliverable D7.4.

	Action	Technical Committee	Responsible	Date
1	Follow up of TCs standardisation activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO/TC 255 Biogas - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence 	UNE	Continuous (Month 12-42)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO/TC 207 Environmental management - ISO/TC 34 Food products - ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal 		
2	Delivering reports to TCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO/TC 255 Biogas - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence - ISO/TC 207 Environmental management - ISO/TC 34 Food products - ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal 	UNE	Month 12-18
3	Participation in a SC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO/TC 215/SC1 <i>Genomics informatics</i> 	partners	If relevant, when SC meets
4	Information to TCs on workshops and conferences	All relevant	UNE	When relevant

2. CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the review of the standardization landscape, we realised that there were not European and International technical committees with direct relationship in GLOMICAVE project, but there are many international technical committees with standards or projects of interest to GLOMICAVE project.

For find out which were the main committees to disseminate the activities of GLOMICAVE project, a survey was sent to specify the technical bodies to report.

For this reason, the objective of the survey was to obtain information on specific standards or aspects that could be standardised and serve as a link between technical committees and GLOMICAVE partners. Almost all partners participated filling in the survey, providing valuable information regarding technical bodies and future standardisation proposals, what will be important to next activities.

In addition, a standardisation proposal was identified as interesting for the GLOMICAVE project (ISO/TS 8392) and three partners are interested in participating in ISO to develop this technical specification, for what these partners shall first request to participate in the mirror technical committees of their countries (for which UNE will facilitate the data of the contact person of their standardisation bodies) and then to request the accreditation as a national expert in ISO/TC 215/SC1, where the technical specification will be developed.

These tasks will be carried out over the next months, and the actions and results will be included in the review of this deliverable.

3. REFERENCES

- [1] CENELEC Website (www.cenelec.eu)
- [2] CEN/CENELEC Projex Online database (projex.cen.eu) (restricted to authorized users)
- [3] ISO Website (www.iso.org)
- [4] ISO Project Portal (isotc.iso.org) (restricted to authorized users)
- [5] IEC Website (www.iec.ch)
- [6] Online Browsing Platform (OBP, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/>)